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Reversible SOC System Development and Testing: Status at AVL and Outlook

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Abstract

A reversible solid oxide cell system layout has been developed and tested as a proof-of-concept (PoC) system. The focus was to reach a simplified system layout in terms of the number of balance of plant (BoP) components, while enabling a high flexibility of the system and an efficient heat management including internal water evaporation. The 4.5/1.5kW ($P_{EC,el}/P_{FC,el}$) PoC system included the core functionalities, such as the main components for heat management and instrumentation. The PoC system was validated on a testbench, which provided media and electricity supply, as well as the automation system. The operation was carried out 100 hours without stack module and 500 hours with stack module primarily in manual operation. Various operating points in fuel cell (FC), as well as in electrolysis (EC) mode were tested, hot idle concepts investigated and switchover routines from FC to EC and vice versa elaborated. The PoC system showed very good operability in terms of flexible heat management in full-, as well as in part load operation and manual switch-over times lower than 15 minutes.

Based on this platform a fully functional rSOC carrier with a reasonable power range and automation is being developed, which will be integrated in a “real-world” simulation environment to show applicability of the technology in the context of renewable energy systems (RES).

Introduction

Besides the potential to reach highest energy conversion efficiencies, solid oxide fuel cells are a technology with the capability to be operated in fuel cell mode to produce electricity by using gaseous fuel, as well as to produce gaseous fuel by using electricity. Thereby not only hydrogen or water, but also carbonaceous feedstocks can be utilized and converted. For both operation modes the same set of cells can be used. Therefore, reversible solid oxide cell (rSOC) systems have great potential to serve in future energy systems as a cost efficient energy conversion solution. To enable the reverse operation of solid oxide cells in real world applications, appropriate systems have to be developed. This, on the other hand, constitutes a challenge, due to the high temperatures and the different characteristics of the two operation modes.

Within the project “Aurora”, which was successfully completed by the end of 2019, AVL developed a rSOC system process design. The focus was set on flexible heat management with integrated steam generation and overall process simplicity, while aiming for as high efficiencies as possible. The novel process concept was realized in the form of a proof-of-concept (PoC) system, which was tested on a test bench at the premises of AVL. The tests approved the potential of the process design and revealed also potential for improvements. Based on this developments and gained know-how, a fully-functional rSOC system is currently under development in a follow-up project, called “Fully integrated reversible solid oxide cell system” – “FIRST”.

1. Scientific Approach

Within the Aurora project, a rSOC system concept at a scale of 33kW/100kW (P_{el_SOFC}/P_{el_SOEC}) was targeted. Based on 0-D process simulations and in an iterative process a novel system flowsheet was developed.

Thereby the focus laid on:

- System efficiency in fuel cell and electrolyzer operation mode
- Heat management
- Internal steam generation
- Controllability
- Minimization of balance-of-plant (BoP) components
- Availability of BoP components

A major challenge in the development of rSOC systems are the very different characteristics of the operation modes. In fuel cell operation mode high amounts of heat are produced via highly exothermal reactions inside the stack. This heat needs to be removed from the stack, which is mainly done via air supply on the air-side of the stack resulting in a significant air-flow. In electrolysis mode, endothermal reactions occur at the stack and hence leading to a much lower required air flow. Thus, besides completely different fuel feed compositions, also the air flow differ significantly between the two operation modes. These characteristics need to be considered and lead to a trade-off in the system design.

The final resulting system concept was scaled down to a stack power rating of 1.5kW/4.5kW (P_{el_SOFC}/P_{el_SOEC}) and reduced to a PoC system, which contained the key functionalities of the novel layout, such as the core heat management components and its control functions. However anode gas recirculation was not considered in the PoC setup. Other required functionalities, such as power supply, automation system and software, gas

supply and safety instrumentations were planned to be covered by a testbed. Hardware specifications were derived from the process simulations of the PoC system. Controlling strategies and error handlings were developed accordingly.

Figure 1: PoC Design

Based on the specifications and supplier feedback, the PoC system was designed mechanically with two different BoP settings, the components were procured, the system set up and prepared for testing. The final mechanical 3D design is shown in Figure 1. The PoC system used a stand-alone stack module, therefore, the BoP components were integrated as another stand-alone unit by itself. The focus was here to cover all main functionalities, but not to reach a high level of an integrated design.

2. Proof-of-Concept Testing

Setup on Testbed

Figure 2 shows the PoC installation on the testbed. On the right hand side, the BoP unit is connected to the gas supply of the test bed. On the left hand side the stack module is connected to the BoP unit likewise. The feed gases are pre-conditioned in the BoP unit before entering the stack module. The stack outlet gases are then post-conditioned in the BoP unit before leaving the system into the exhaust system of the test bed. Electrically, all actuators and sensors/measurement devices were connected to the respective interfaces of the test bed. Automation system, error handlings and visualization were also covered by the test bed.

Figure 2: rSOC PoC Setup on Testbed

Testing Plan

The overall test plan included several testing phases, as shown in Figure 3. After the PoC system commissioning on the testbed, a pre-phase testing was done where the BoP unit was tested without stack module. This testing phase aimed for the validation of key functionalities of the BoP unit. Thereby the BoP unit was heated up and cooled down several times with the aim to reach certain stable temperature levels at the stack inlets. This heat up - cool down cycle tests lasted for about 100 hours. After the feasibility was proven and the milestone reached, the stack module was added to the setting. The tests including the stack module were conducted with two different BoP variants. Setup 1 was tested around 100h, decommissioned and adapted. Setup 2 was tested around 400h. Both settings were operated 24/7 mostly in manual operation by an operator.

Figure 3: Overview testing scheme

The BoP setup 2 showed a much better controllability than setup 1 due to improved components. The PoC system was tested with various settings in fuel cell mode, electrolysis mode and in different hot-idle states. However, the main focus laid on the switchover routines from fuel cell into electrolysis mode and vice versa, to prove the viability of the whole system concept.

3. Results

Simulation Results

A main outcome of the process simulations was the efficiency potential of the rSOC platform as developed. In steam electrolysis operation theoretically efficiencies up to 79% ($P_{el,DC} - LHV$) could be achieved. In fuel cell operation, based on hydrogen fuel and depending on the actual stack technology, efficiencies between 50 -60% ($LHV - P_{el,DC}$) could be feasible.

Experimental/Testing Results

As described before, the feasibility of heating up the system according to the key functionalities constituted a milestone within the validation process. Figure 4 shows the temperature evolution over time of the stack inlet and outlet temperatures while heating the PoC system up to full load operation conditions in fuel cell mode. Since the focus of the heat up was not the timing, but reliability, the temperature ramp was thereby kept low of around 0.5 K/min. Besides the pre-phase testing without stack module, the system heat up was executed one time for each setup.

Steady state fuel cell operation in full load resulted in an overall electrical system efficiency of ~55% ($LHV - P_{el,DC}$) by using a hydrogen-nitrogen mixture as fuel and ~52% ($LHV - P_{el,DC}$) by using a hydrogen-steam mixture as fuel. Hereby parasitic loads such as for the gas supply, which were covered by the test bed, are not considered.

Due to safety restrictions on the available test bed it was not possible to operate the PoC system in full electrolysis load. This lead to heat management issues and cool down of the system to a certain level when operating the system in part load, caused by the “loose” design integration.

Figure 4: System heat-up temperature evolution

However, stable part load operation was feasible and switchover routines were elaborated at lower temperatures. Figures 5 a.-d. show two switchover routines. Figure 5 a. shows the total current supply and draw at the switchover from electrolysis mode to fuel cell mode and in Figure 5 b. the related average cell voltage is shown. The analogue charts are

shown for the switchover from fuel cell mode to electrolysis mode in Figure 5 c.-d.. Although the PoC system was operated in a manual manner, which means that the test bed operator had to change all settings manually, switchover times lower than 15 minutes could be reached in both directions. However, certain limitations existed. As shown in Figure 5 a. and b. the current ramp up in fuel cell mode was restricted by the low voltage, because the part load operation in electrolysis mode lead to a cool down of the stack. Lower stack temperatures increase ohmic losses and thereby decrease the cell voltage, which limits the current that can be drawn. An increase of the stack power required a heat up, which took time. It is key to keep in both operation modes the same stack temperature levels to enable fast switching and ramp up to full load operation. The main challenge in the switchover routine from fuel cell mode to steam electrolysis mode is the ramp up of the steam supply. It constitutes a limitation, if less steam is supplied to the stack than the amount which is required for full load operation.

Figure 5 a-d.: Manual switch-over modulations

All in all, the key functionality of the system concept was validated, the main targets were met and potential improvements were identified.

Outlook

Based on the results of the “Aurora” project, a follow-up system development is currently in work within the project “FIRST”, where a fully functional system is being developed.

The targets of the project are:

- setup of a fully automated rSOC system with internal steam generation
- integration into a building which contains a RES-PV installation
- implementation of predictive controlling algorithms
- fast operation mode switching times < 5 minutes
- highest efficiencies up to 60% in fuel cell mode with hydrogen fuel
- highest efficiencies up to 75% in steam electrolysis mode

To reach the goals, the rSOC system requires a well-executed mechanical design to minimize heat losses throughout the system and a mature automation system with appropriate controlling strategies. It will be set up and integrated into a “real-world” renewable energy system (RES) environment, where long term tests ~7000h are planned. The fully functional system will have a scale of 5kW/15kW ($P_{FC,el}/P_{EC,el}$) and should prove the applicability of the technology in the context of renewable energy systems. A key challenge is thereby the intermittency of electricity production by renewable energy sources and how rSOC systems can be integrated in the best way.

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